

Omani Students' Perceptions Of Private Tuition: The Structural Equation Modeling Approach

Rashid Mohammed Al Hajri, Hamood Ahmed Al-huneini, Kodhandaraman Chinnathambi

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 22,2023</p> <p>Accepted: March 23,2024</p> <p>Keywords : Academic Performance, Assessment, Private Tutoring, Study Skills, Self-Confidence</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10856826</p>	<p><i>This study aims to design a structural equation model to explain better the reason for the prevalence of private tuition in Oman and its impact on Omani students studying in high and higher secondary schools. It seeks to answer the following research questions: Does the hypothesized structural equation model fit well? How do Omani students in high and higher secondary schools perceive the impact of private tuition on their academic performance? The study adopted a quantitative research method. Data were collected from Omani students (in grades 9 to 12) attending private tuition (N=1111) across Oman. This structural equation modeling-based private tuition model outlines the relations among different types of independent and dependent variables and constructs. The model was tested using adequate fitting indices like the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI), Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA), and Comparative Fit Index (IFI). The results of the proposed model confirm the hypothesized latent constructs and theoretical validity of probed factors. Along these lines, the perceptions of Omani students in high and higher secondary schools show that private tuition positively influences their academic performance.</i></p>

Introduction

Education systems have developed over the years, and assessments and exams have become essential to measure students' achievement. Many education systems rely heavily on exams to ensure fairness, mainly when many students compete for limited higher education seats and scholarships. Thus, students and their families have been looking for ways that enable learners to maximize their scores in school exams. Therefore, many parents hire private tutors to help their children in various subjects. At first, private tuition was a sole practice for wealthy families. However, this idea became a global issue (2014 Kwo& Bray), and the demand for private tutors increased. In a way, private tuition became a parallel education system that goes along with school systems in many countries, and many families perceive it as an obligation (Zhang,2021).

In Oman, private tuition has gained popularity over the last two decades (Alrawahi,2021). Therefore, studying this phenomenon has become necessary to unveil different aspects of this issue and its impact on Omani students and the school system in general. In this context, many points related to private tuition, such as the percentage of prevalence of private lessons among Omani school students, the most common forms of private lessons, the subjects for which students take private tuition, criteria used for selecting a private teacher, the place for private tuition, time allotted for tuition, money spent on tuition, remain unexplored.

Although students and parents invest a lot of time and money in private tuition, few research studies have been carried out in Oman, so details related to private tutoring are not available. Consequently, the stakeholders are still determining whether private tuition positively impacts Omani students' self-confidence, study skills, and academic performance. More research is needed regarding private tuition in Oman. Hence, this research aims to study the effect of private tuition on student's self-confidence, study skills, and academic performance in high schools and higher secondary schools in Oman. This study is significant because it tries to fill the research gap and has implications for students, parents, teachers, and policymakers.

Review of related literature

In Japan, private lessons are inclusive and more organized, as in 2017, they constituted a value of \$969 billion in the markets (Zhang,2021). In China, private lessons have expanded over the 1990s and developed the world's most extensive system for private tuition (2017 Bray & Zhang). In 2020, official statistics estimated that over half a million companies with more than 11 million employees are working on providing private tuition in China. The situation is not better in South Korea since their national statistics show that 74.5% of Korean students k-12 received private tuition in 2019 (KOSIS, 2020).

Davies & Aurini (2006) have found that 24% of parents in Canada hire private teachers to provide academic support to their children. The percentage appears to get higher when it comes to the Arab world. For example, a

study conducted by the Information Centre of the Egyptian Cabinet 2009 found that 61%-77% of students receive private tuition across all school levels. On the other hand, official Egyptian statistics show that private lessons prohibited by Egyptian laws cost families around 15 billion Egyptian Pounds (Information Center, 2010).

However, in Arab Gulf countries, official statistics are not available regarding this issue, which causes an ambiguous situation regarding the reality of the spread of this phenomenon. Neither teachers nor students publicly speak about private tuition since all Gulf states consider it illegal for teachers to provide it. However, studies show that the phenomenon is spreading in the Gulf countries. For example, a study in Kuwait found that 67.8% of secondary students go for private tuition (AlSalhi&others,2011). Also, in UAE, Jalal (2006) found that 19.3% go for private lessons, which rose to 27% in 2018 (Hamid, 2018). In Saudi Arabia, 45.9% of male and 56.6% of secondary students receive private lessons (AlZayoodi,2018). A Ministry of Education in Oman (2018) study showed that 47,7) go for private tuition.

Students go for private lessons for socio-economic reasons (Bary,2014). Also, the school's environment can be behind other reasons for the spread of private tuition; crowded classrooms, low quality of teaching, and complex curriculum may lead students to go for extra lessons (Bary&Lykin, 2012).

Al Ghanim (2017) believes that the main reason for the spread of private lessons is the challenging math topics students get in schools that do not correspond to students' abilities. Such activities reduce teacher-student classroom interaction and students' interest in these topics. Isawi (2018) thinks that students' absence and lack of autonomy force parents to opt for private tuition to get high grades. Al Daami (2017) has found that students' views suggest that they go for private tuition to get the high grades required for university enrolment in specific programs, especially for complex topics in some school subjects.

However, Bray and Kwo (2014) see that private tuition spreads among students who need remedial work and extra support when dealing with their peers or school learning procedures. This becomes obvious with other challenges, such as crowded classrooms. Hatamela (2021) lists several reasons; students' weakness in some school subjects comes at the top of this list. He also says that schools need more effort to raise students' awareness of the danger these private lessons may bring to the learners and the school system since they encourage students to neglect classes and promote carelessness.

Others believe that there are reasons related to the teachers who play a role in spreading private tuition as they gain financial benefits. These benefits encourage teachers suffering from economic restraints, especially in developing countries, to go for private tuition outside school hours (Isawi,2018). Teachers' low income is one of the main reasons for the spread of private teaching through which they seek to lift their living standards. Teachers' lack of incentives has a role in promoting working extra hours as private tutors (Hatamela, 2021).

There are also reasons related to family, such as the over-pampering of children that parents follow when providing education to their children, which leads learners to be too dependent on studying (Hatamela, 2021). In addition, many families tend to imitate other families in providing extra support to children without considering the need. This practice might be due to helping learners score high grades (Hamid, 2018). Zhang (2014) sees that high achiever students are more willing to go for private lessons than challenged students, and families consider this as part of their investment in children's education.

Private lessons differ in nature as community orientation and policies around them vary. The first type is official. The educational institutions promote some private lessons, and governments pay extra incentives for teachers to encourage them to provide extra student support. So they can score high in national and international exams (Bray & Kwo, 2014). The second type is unofficial, as it does not come through the educational organization. It is usually understood as an unofficial individual agreement between parents and individual teachers. This type is spreading more as lessons are provided outside school premises in various houses, public places, and libraries. The third type is organized by private institutions registered to provide extra complementary support for learners. These organizations offer multiple services, and parents are to choose what they think is better for their child and their budgets. Lessons can be provided for groups or individual students, face-to-face or online. Such organizations have official licenses in Turkey and Japan (Bray & Kwo, 2014).

Overall, as private lessons offer solutions to some of the problems learners and families may face in the education process, they may also challenge the social, economic, and educational community.

Objective of the study

The objectives of the study are as follows.

1. To study the demographic profile of the students studying in private tuition.
2. To examine the effectiveness of the private tuition model for assessing students' perception of private tuition.
3. To examine the goodness of fit indices of the model.

Research questions

1. Does the hypothesized structural equation model have a good fit?

2. How do Omani students in high and higher secondary schools perceive the impact of private tuition on their academic performance?

Hypotheses

- Null Hypothesis (Ho): The hypothesized model does not have a good fit.
- Null Hypothesis (Ho): Omani students' perceptions do not show any positive influence of private tuition on their academic performance.

Data collection and sample

This research adopted a quantitative method and disseminated a self-prepared questionnaire to collect participant data. A five-point Likertscale (5 indicating strongly agree, and 1 indicating strongly disagree) was used to increase the measure's sensitivity. The study used both the primary and secondary data. The secondary data was collected from various indexed journals and prominent websites. Primary data was collected based on the perceptions of students studying in private tuitions in different regions of Oman. Data was collected from 1111 students in grades nine, ten, eleven, and twelve invarious Oman's high and higher secondary schools. Student's opinions about private tuition were elicited from students attending private tuition. One thousand one hundred eleven students who answered the questionnaireattended private tuition.

Data Analysis

Collected data were analyzed with the help of software package SPSS and analysis of moment structure (AMOS) 16. Statistical techniques like descriptive analysis, reliability analysis, exploratory factor analysis, and confirmatory factor analysis were used to evaluate the ineffectiveness of private tuition. Structural equation modeling and partial lease squareswere used for data analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Demographic profile of students who take private tuition.

S.No.	Characteristics	Categories	No.of Respondents	Percentage%
1	Gender	Male	550	49.5
		Female	561	50.5
2	Grade	9	180	16.2
		10	247	22.2
		11	306	27.5
		12	378	34
3	Family Spending Money	Less than 50 Rials	446	40.1
		50-150 Rials		
		151-200 Rials	312	28.1
		More than 200 Rials	50	4.5
		I don't know	92	8.3
4	Average Score		211	19.0
		more than 90%		
		80%-90%	311	28%
		70%-79%	415	34.4%
		247	22.2%	
		138	12.4%	

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of students who participated in the study. As per table 1, out of 1,111 respondents, 49.5% were male and 50.5% were female. Regarding grade, 16.2% were in grade 9, 22.2% were in grade 10, 27.5% were in grade 11 and 34% were in grade 12. Concerning governorate, 11.8% were from Sharqia North, 14.3% were from Sharqia South, 25.7% were Batina North, 13.1% were from Batina South, 4.9% from Dakhliya, 0.3% were from Wosta, 1.5% were from Musandam, 0.3% were from Buraimi, 6.4% from Dahira, 3.4% were from Dofar, and 18.4 % were from Muscat. Regarding students receiving social security funds, 10.8% said 'yes,' 76.1% said 'no,' and 13.1% said 'I don't know.' Average family spending on private tuition was as follows: 40.1% said they received less than 50 rials, 28.1% said they received 50-150 rials, 4.5% said they received 151-200 rials, and 8.3% said they received more than 200 rials. 19% said they did not know. Regarding parents' education, 5% said their mother had no education. 14.6% of fathers and 17.6% of mothers had completed less than grade 12. 27.5% of fathers and 28.2% of mothers had completed grade 12. 23.1% of

fathers and 24.5 % of mothers had completed B.A. 16.2% of fathers and 10% of mothers had completed M.A. or PhD. 18.5% of fathers and 19.3% of mothers had completed other types of education.

Table 2: Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Impact	0.915	0.923	0.926	0.536
PT_improvement	0.782	0.785	0.859	0.604
Pimpact_	0.731	0.778	0.827	0.548

Table 3: Discriminant Validity

Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Nimpact	PT_improvement	Pimpact_
Nimpact	0.732		
PT_improvement	-0.148	0.777	
Pimpact_	0.066	0.355	0.740

Table 4: Collinearity Statistics (VIF Table)

	VIF
a16_1	1.506
a16_2	1.510
a16_3	1.702
a16_4	1.697
a221	1.685
a2210	1.344
a2211	1.888
a2212	1.537
a2213	2.087
a2214	1.367
a2216	1.401
a222	1.862
a223	2.255
a224	2.572
a225	2.440
a226	2.603
a227	2.196
a228	1.563
a229	1.287

Scale Development and Validity

To examine the proposed research model, analyses of both measurement and structural model using the partial least squares (PLS) algorithm. The PLS is the most appropriate and user-friendly software to simultaneously test measurement and structural models, as the researcher can simultaneously measure direct, indirect, and moderation effects. Both formative and reflective indicators are used to test the proposed model.

For the formative constructs, positive impact (5 items) and negative impact (11 items) were used to assess the strength of the relationship between measured items and the construct. The result shows (Table 2) that the measured items significantly explained the latent construct's positive and negative impacts. The variance inflation factor was then performed to assess the multicollinearity. VIF values of more than ten would suggest the existence of multicollinearity and create doubt about the validity of the formative measurement. The result shows that the values varied from 1.287 to 2.603 for all these items. It is exhibited that there are no multicollinearity issues with these formative constructs.

It also tested the positive impact of the predictor constructs positive impact (Pimpact) and negative impact (Nimpact) on the dependent factor frequency of Improvement by using Private Tuition (PT_Improvement). The assessment of the measurement model for the reflective construct included an estimation of internal consistency for reliability and a test for convergent and discriminant validity. The internal consistency was calculated using Cronbach's alpha construct reliability (C.R.) and average variance extracted (AVE). It is suggested that the Cronbach alpha and construct reliability coefficient should be a minimum of 0.7. The result shows the internal consistency Cronbach alpha for positive impact (0.731) and negative impact (0.915) and also the composite reliability for these constructs Pimpact (0.827) and Nimpact (0.926). The Average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity are also considered to measure the internal consistency and validate the scale. The AVE should be a minimum of 0.5, but the result shows Pimpact (0.548) and Nimpact (0.536). Discriminant validity is used here to examine whether the correlation between the variables is lower than the square root of the average variance extracted. There is evident internal consistency among the formative construct positive impact (Pimpact) and negative impact (Nimpact) as the measurement result of Cronbach alpha, composite reliability, Average variance extracted, and discriminant validity coefficients are satisfied and met the minimum requirement.

As per Table 7 – it is clear that the values of all the items (Pimpact, Nimpact, and Improvement) are above the suggested value of 0.5 (Hair et al., 2006). According to Bollen (1989a), the higher the probability associated with Chi-square, the closer the fit is between the hypothesized model and the perfect fit. The test of our null hypothesis Hothat Private Tuition is a three-factor structure, as shown in Figure 1, yielded a chi-square of 1187.464 with 167 degrees of freedom and a probability of less than 0.0001 (P <0.0001). It suggests that the data's fit to the hypothesized model is not entirely adequate. As per the result, Chi-square statistics with p = 0.000 do not show the model's good fit. However, the model can be considered as the other fit indices (GFI, GFI, RMCA) satisfy the referred value. According to Schumaker and Lomax (1996), a sample size of over 200 (3500 in this study) could affect the Chi-square to indicate a significant probability level (p=0.00). Consequently, this model is considered for further interpretation in the goodness of fit measures.

Figure 1 Structural Equation Model

Table 5: Regression Weights (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
PT_Improvement	<---	Nimpact	-0.232	.031	-6.312	***	

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
PT_Improvement	<---	Pimpact	.462	.039	10.234	***	
a16_1	<---	PT_Improvement	.644				
a16_2	<---	PT_Improvement	.644	.066	16.796	***	
a16_3	<---	PT_Improvement	.725	.065	18.129	***	
a16_4	<---	PT_Improvement	.739	.065	18.295	***	
a2216	<---	Pimpact	.650				
a2215	<---	Pimpact	.415	.069	11.359	***	
a2210	<---	Pimpact	.613	.072	15.555	***	
a229	<---	Pimpact	.578	.070	14.916	***	
a2214	<---	Nimpact	.508				
a2213	<---	Nimpact	.738	.094	16.560	***	
a2212	<---	Nimpact	.597	.079	14.761	***	
a2211	<---	Nimpact	.704	.090	16.169	***	
a228	<---	Pimpact	.707	.069	16.887	***	
a227	<---	Nimpact	.763	.093	16.823	***	
a226	<---	Nimpact	.783	.095	17.030	***	
a225	<---	Nimpact	.768	.096	16.881	***	
a224	<---	Nimpact	.804	.096	17.232	***	
a223	<---	Nimpact	.766	.094	16.853	***	
a222	<---	Nimpact	.686	.085	15.955	***	
a221	<---	Nimpact	.620	.087	15.091	***	

Nimpact - Negative impact & Pimpact - Positive impact

Table 5 shows the standardized estimate, its standard error (S.E.), and the estimate divided by the standard error (C.R. for Critical Ratio). Under the column P, the probability value associated with the null hypothesis is given. The regression analysis revealed the influence of the two independent factors on the Improvement of exam grades (a16_1), self-confidence during exams (a16_2), study skills (a16_3), and learning strategies (a16_4)(PT_Improvement). The above regression weight shows that the five statements coded as Pimpact are the most influencing as the regression weight is 0.462, next to the 11 statements coded as Nimpact with 0.232 regression weight. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. The visual representations of results suggest that the relationship between the dependent and independent variables is stronger. The overall regression model shows that the factors of Pimpact and Nimpact have significantly influenced the dependent factor PT_Improvement, and the model represented R^2 0.232, i.e., 23%, the independent factors are explaining the dependent factor (PT_Improvement). The factor (a228) results reveal that 70% (0.707) of poorly achieving students show that private tuition has significantly contributed to their academic performance, and regarding the four factors of PT_Improvement, 64% (0.644) of students agreed that private tuition had improved their exam grades and

increased their self-confidence. Similarly, 72% (0.725) of students show Improvement in study skills and 73% (0.739) in learning strategies due to private tuition. However, 80% (0.804) of students revealed that it causes distraction and loss of time.

Table 7: Goodness Fit Indices

Fit Indices	Results	Suggested values
Chi-square	1187.464 (0.000) DF- 167	P-value >0.05
Chi-square/degree of freedom ($\chi^2/d.f.$)	7.11	≤ 5.00 (Hair et al., 1998)
Comparative Fit Index (CFI)	0.891	>0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)	0.901	>0.90 (Hair et al. 2006)
Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)	0.876	> 0.90 (Daire et al., 2008)
Normated Fit Index (NFI)	0.875	≥ 0.90 (Hu and Bentler, 1999)
Incremental Fit Index (IFI)	0.891	Approaches 1
Tucker Lewis Index (TLI)	0.876	≥ 0.90 (Hair et al., 1998)
Root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA)	0.074	< 0.08 (Hair et al., 2006)
Parsimony goodness-of-fit index (PGFI)	0.717	Within 0.5 (Mulaik et al., 1989)

Evaluation of model fit

Model fit indicators depict various indicators of goodness of fit for the proposed model and their acceptance values. In order to evaluate model fit, various well-known goodness-of-fit indices are used (Byrne,1998; Hair et al., 1992; Jöreskog & Sörbom, 1996). These include the chi-square χ^2 , the comparative fit index, the unadjusted goodness-of-fit indices, the normal fit index, the Tucker-Lewis Index, the root mean square error of approximation, and the standardized root mean square error residual. Goodness-of-fit indices provide cutoff values to evaluate data-model fit. Hu and Bentler, 1999 recommend using combinations of Goodness-of-fit indices to obtain a comprehensive evaluation of model fit. The criterion values with good model fit for in structural equation modeling are comparative fit index (CFI) > 0.891, Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI) > 0.876, root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) < 0.074, and square error residual (SRMR) <0.0817. Some researchers suggest that these cutoff values are too stringent and that the findings may have limited generalizability (Beauducel&Wittmann, 2005; Fan &Sivo, 2005; Marsh et al., 2004). Therefore, it is recommended that absolute fit indices and incremental fit indices (such as CFI, GFI, NFI, and TLI), the cutoff values should be above 0.90, and fit indices based on residuals matrix values (such as RMSEA and SRMR) should be below 0.10 or 0.05. Figure 1 depicts the model with standardized regression weights extracted from AMOS graphics.

Conclusion and Implications

This research aimed to empirically analyze the factors determining Omani students' perception of private tuition using a structural equation model. This study affirms and develops an instrument of private tuition against the backdrop of Oman's high and higher secondary school education. The proposed model was developed and calibrated using data collected from Oman's students in grades nine, ten, eleven, and twelve. The hypothesized three-factor model fits the sample data. Based on the viability and statistical significance of critical parameter estimates (CFI, AGFI, NFI, IFI, TLI, and RMSEA), it can be concluded that the three-factor model shown in Figure 1 represents an adequate description of private tuition and its positive impact on Omani students. As the goodness of fit indices support model fit and these emphasized indices indicate the acceptability of this structure model, the null hypothesis rejected. Based on the regression weight, private tuition positively impacts students. Thus, the study confirms the previous findings of Entrich (2018), Guil, Bos. (2014), Ireson&Rushforth (2005), and Silova& Bray (2005) state that private tuition improves students' academic achievement. All students who participated in this study, most notably the poorly achieving students, confirm that private tuition has significantly improved their academic performance.

The study has implications for all stakeholders, including students, parents, teachers, and policymakers. In the current competitive environment, private tuition should be encouraged among poorly achieving students and students who want to get high scores to get good academic placements. Parents who want their children to do better academically might sustain the practice of sending them to private tuition.

Limitations and Future Research

The study has its limitations. The study adopted only a quantitative research method, so qualitative or mixed methods might be adopted in future research. Also, the study examined only the tutees' perspectives but did not include parents' or tutors' perspectives. Similarly, instructional quality, the tutor's educational background, and

the context of tuition should have been explored. Since these factors can significantly affect the study results, further research can be carried out in those areas to draw a valid decision regarding private tuition.

Bio-note of the authors

Dr. Rashid Alhajri is an associated professor in Educational foundation at A'Sharqiyah University-Ibra, Oman. He received his PhD from the University of Science, Malaysia in comparative education in 2007. He used to be an educational expert at Ministry of education, Oman for nine years 2009-2018. His areas of interest include educational foundation, comparative education, and Educational administration. ORCID ID - 0000-0003-0428-4891

Hamood Al Huneini is a Ph.D. holder from the University of Leeds. He is currently a lecturer at the University of Technology and Applied Sciences. He is a former English Language Supervisor at the Ministry of Education in Oman. ORCID ID - 0009-0001-3783-8929

Dr. Kodhandaraman Chinnathambi is a Lecturer in English at the University of Technology and Applied Sciences-Ibra, Oman. He received his PhD from the University of Madras, India. He is a member of the Board of Directors of TESOL Oman. Also, he is the Editor of the Oman Journal of ELT. His area of interest includes ELT, Theory, and Literature. ORCID ID: 0000-0002-1289-9290

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Author Information

Dr. Rashid Mohammed Al Hajri
 Department of Education
 A' Sharqiyah University, Oman.

Dr. Hamood Ahmed Al-huneini
 Preparatory Studies Centre
 University of Technology and Applied Sciences-Ibra,
 Oman

Dr. Kodhandaraman Chinnathambi
 Preparatory Studies Centre
 University of Technology and Applied Sciences-
 Ibra, Oman
